

AXIOLOGICAL INTERJECTIONS IN UZBEK
DISCOURSE

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ABSTRACT

The article analyzes the place of interjections in Uzbek within the system of axiological lexis, consistently outlining their positive and negative types from semantic and pragmatic perspectives. The findings show that interjections not only encode subjective evaluation but also reflect socio-cultural values.

Interjections in Uzbek are independent lexical units forming a special class that conveys people's feelings and meanings such as exclamation, urging, driving away, and calling. The primary function of interjections is to express the speaker's attitude; therefore, since interjections reflect subjective evaluation, they are included among the layers of axiological lexis.

Semantically, there are emotional interjections (*obbo*), imperative interjections (*pisht*), and those that do not belong to these two groups (*xo'sh-xo'sh*). It is precisely emotional interjections that directly convey axiological evaluation; in the other two types, an axiological reading is not inherent but may sometimes be implied by context. Emotional interjections are divided into two groups—positive and negative.

Positive emotional interjections express the following meanings:

1. Interjections expressing compassion and kindness — *lye, voyey, voy*;
2. Interjections expressing joy, delight, and pleasure — *voy, ho, ehe, o'hho', ho*;
3. Words conveying admiration and enjoyment — *o, hay-hay, o*;
4. Interjections expressing satisfaction, pride, dignity, benevolence — *e-ha, eh, ehe, o'ho', o'h-ho', voy, ehe, ha-ya, e-ha*;
5. Interjections expressing calling, warning, and affirmation — *hay-hay, ha*.

Negative emotional interjections serve to express the following meanings:

1. Interjections of objection, discontent, complaint, lament — *ha, ho, voyeye, voy, e, o'h, oh, Ey, xudo, obbo*;
2. Interjections conveying disgust, anger, irritation, rage, hatred — *e, e, eh, he*;
3. Interjections expressing pity and regret — *he, attang, oh, eh*;
4. Interjections expressing irony, mockery, sarcasm, reproach — *o, e, obbo, hoy-hoy, ho, e*;
5. Interjections for reprimand, warning, unexpected situations — *hay-hay, iya, e*;

6. Interjections expressing fright, panic, and fear — *oh, o, voy*;

7. Interjections of grief, sorrow, misfortune, distress, remorse — *oh, e, o*;

8. Interjections expressing surprise, astonishment, wonder, resentment — *iyi, iya, iye-voy*.

Emotional interjections are a distinct layer of axiological lexis that convey the speaker's positive or negative evaluation directly through lexical-intonational means. Unlike other units, these forms function in the text as independent items, delivering subjective evaluation clearly and concisely without being syntactically bound to other grammatical means.

“Obbo, endi shuyam bormid?” Yodgor chiroqni yoqdi. Gaz plitaga qo'yilaverib sarg'ayib ketgan choygumni bir chekkaga olib qo'ydi. Plashinging qorini qoqib, karavotga tashladi. (O'. Hoshimov, *Sevgi qissalari*)

In this example, the interjection *obbo* functions as an independent lexical unit within the clause, directly expressing Yodgor's fatigue and dissatisfaction. From an axiological standpoint, it carries a negative meaning, succinctly signaling objection and complaint.

Whether interjections appear with positive or negative meaning depends on context. However, there are interjections that express exclusively positive or negative meanings even without context. For instance, the interjection *ura* conveys only a positive meaning.

Beyond emotional interjections, there are also interjections expressing customs and social etiquette which qualify as axiological lexical units—for example, greetings (*hormang*), congratulations and farewells (*hayr*), encouragement (*qulluq, ofarin*), expressions of thanks and gratitude (*rahmat, marhamat*). This type of interjection likewise represents a variety of axiological lexis, articulating socio-cultural values and, as a positive evaluative resource, reinforcing norms of speech culture.

Interjections in Uzbek enhance the emotive coloring of discourse and clearly convey the speaker's subjective evaluation. Categorized into positive and negative groups, they express not only personal feelings but also the socio-cultural values of the community. Therefore, studying interjections as an important component of axiological lexis constitutes a significant issue in linguistics.

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